

Formulation, Characterization and In Vitro Evaluation of Lafutidine Nano suspension Prepared by Precipitation Method

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Lafutidine is a BCS Class II antiulcer drug exhibiting poor aqueous solubility and dissolution-limited bioavailability. The present study aimed to formulate and evaluate Lafutidine Nano suspensions using the precipitation method to improve drug dissolution and potential oral bioavailability.

Methods: Lafutidine Nano suspensions were prepared by nanoprecipitation using Poloxamer 188, Pluronic F127, and sodium lauryl sulfate (SLS) as stabilizers. Twelve formulations (F1–F12) were developed using different polymer-to-drug ratios. The prepared Nano suspensions were evaluated for drug-excipient compatibility, entrapment efficiency, particle size, zeta potential, surface morphology, in vitro drug release, and release kinetics.

Results: FTIR studies confirmed the absence of significant interactions between Lafutidine and formulation excipients. Entrapment efficiency ranged from $89.75 \pm 1.21\%$ to $98.47 \pm 1.68\%$. The optimized formulation (F12) exhibited the highest entrapment efficiency ($98.47 \pm 1.68\%$) and a particle size of approximately 195.14 nm. In vitro dissolution studies demonstrated rapid drug release, with $98.85 \pm 1.02\%$ release within 45 min. Drug release kinetics were best fitted to the first-order model ($R^2 = 0.965$).

Conclusion: The precipitation method successfully produced stable Lafutidine Nano suspensions with enhanced dissolution characteristics. The optimized formulation F12 may represent a promising approach for improving the oral bioavailability of Lafutidine.

Keywords: Lafutidine, Nano suspension, Nanoprecipitation, Pluronic F127, Poloxamer 188, Dissolution Enhancement.

1. INTRODUCTION

Poor aqueous solubility remains one of the major challenges in oral drug delivery. Nearly 40% of newly developed drug molecules exhibit poor water solubility, resulting in inadequate dissolution and reduced oral bioavailability. Nano suspension technology has emerged as an effective strategy for improving the dissolution rate and bioavailability of poorly soluble drugs. [2,10-13]

Lafutidine is a second-generation histamine H₂-receptor antagonist widely used in the treatment of gastric ulcers, duodenal ulcers, and gastroesophageal reflux disease. Due to its poor aqueous solubility, Lafutidine belongs to Biopharmaceutical Classification System (BCS) Class II, where dissolution is the rate-limiting step in drug absorption. Reduction of drug particle size into the nanometer range increases surface area, saturation solubility, and dissolution rate, ultimately enhancing absorption^[18,19,20].

Nano suspensions are submicron colloidal dispersions of pure drug particles stabilized by surfactants and polymers. [10,11] They offer several advantages including improved dissolution, enhanced bioavailability, reduced dose variability, and ease of scale-up. [11-13] Therefore, the present investigation focused on the formulation and evaluation of Lafutidine Nano suspensions using the precipitation method.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Lafutidine was obtained as a gift sample from a pharmaceutical manufacturing company. Poloxamer 188, Pluronic F127, and Sodium Lauryl Sulfate (SLS) were used as stabilizers and surfactants. Ethanol was used as the organic solvent, while distilled water served as the aqueous phase. All chemicals and reagents used in the study were of analytical grade.

2.2 Preformulation Studies

2.2.1 Solubility Studies

The solubility of Lafutidine was determined in various solvents including 0.1 N HCl, phosphate buffer pH 6.8, phosphate buffer pH 7.4, ethanol, and methanol. Excess quantity of drug was added to 10 mL of each solvent in separate stoppered vials. The vials were shaken continuously for 48 h at 25°C using a mechanical shaker to attain equilibrium. The solutions were filtered through Whatman filter paper and suitably diluted. Drug concentration was determined using a UV-visible spectrophotometer. [1,9,16]

2.2.2 Determination of λ_{max} and Calibration Curve

A stock solution of Lafutidine (1000 µg/mL) was prepared in methanol and subsequently diluted using 0.1 N HCl to obtain concentrations ranging from 2–12 µg/mL. Absorbance was measured at 286 nm against a suitable blank. A calibration curve was plotted between concentration and absorbance, and the regression equation was calculated. [1,9]

2.3 Drug–Excipient Compatibility Study

Compatibility studies between Lafutidine and excipients were carried out using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR). Samples of pure drug and optimized formulation were mixed with potassium bromide and compressed into pellets. Spectra were recorded over a wavelength range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} and compared for any changes in characteristic peaks. [1,8]

2.4 Preparation of Lafutidine Nano suspension

Lafutidine Nano suspensions were prepared by the precipitation method. Accurately weighed Lafutidine was dissolved in 2 mL of ethanol to form the organic phase. The aqueous phase was prepared by dissolving different concentrations of stabilizers (Poloxamer 188, Pluronic F127, and SLS) in distilled water.

The organic phase was rapidly injected into the aqueous phase under continuous magnetic stirring at 1200 rpm. Immediate precipitation of drug nanoparticles occurred due to solvent diffusion and supersaturation. Stirring was continued for 1 h to facilitate complete evaporation of ethanol and stabilization of nanoparticles. [1,3,6,8]

Twelve formulations (F1–F12) were prepared by varying polymer and surfactant concentrations while maintaining a constant drug concentration.

2.5 Evaluation of Nano suspensions

2.5.1 Entrapment Efficiency

Entrapment efficiency was determined by ultracentrifugation at 20,000 rpm for 20 min at 5°C. The supernatant containing free drug was analyzed spectrophotometrically at 286 nm. [1,7,8]

Entrapment efficiency (%) was calculated using:

$$EE (\%) = [(Total\ Drug - Free\ Drug)/Total\ Drug] \times 100$$

2.5.2 Particle Size Analysis

Particle size distribution of the optimized formulation was measured using a Malvern Zetasizer. Samples were diluted with distilled water before analysis and measurements were performed in triplicate. [3,10,11]

2.5.3 Zeta Potential Measurement

Zeta potential was determined using a Zetasizer based on electrophoretic mobility measurements. The analysis was performed at room temperature to assess stability of the nano suspension. [4,10]

2.5.4 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Surface morphology and particle shape were examined using scanning electron microscopy. Samples were mounted on aluminum stubs and coated with gold before imaging. [3,6]

2.5.5 *In Vitro* Drug Release Study

Drug release studies were carried out using USP Dissolution Apparatus Type II (Paddle Method). Dissolution medium consisted of 900 mL of 0.1 N HCl maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ with paddle rotation speed of 50 rpm.

Samples were withdrawn at predetermined intervals and replaced with fresh dissolution medium. Drug concentration was determined spectrophotometrically at 286 nm. [1,16,17]

2.6 Drug Release Kinetics

The dissolution data were fitted into various kinetic models including:

- Zero-order model
- First-order model
- Higuchi model
- Korsmeyer–Peppas model

The model exhibiting the highest correlation coefficient (R^2) was considered as the best fit^[1,7].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Solubility Studies

Lafutidine exhibited maximum solubility in 0.1 N HCl compared with phosphate buffer pH 6.8 and pH 7.4. The higher solubility in acidic medium may be attributed to ionization of the drug molecule.

Based on these findings, 0.1 N HCl was selected as the dissolution medium.

3.2 UV Spectrophotometric Analysis

Lafutidine exhibited maximum absorbance at 286 nm. The calibration curve showed excellent linearity within the concentration range of 2–12 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The correlation coefficient was found close to unity, confirming adherence to Beer–Lambert's law.

Fig: 1 Standard calibration curve of Lafutidine in 0.1N HCL

3.3 FTIR Compatibility Studies

FTIR spectra of pure Lafutidine displayed characteristic peaks corresponding to functional groups present in the drug molecule. Similar peaks were observed in the optimized formulation without significant shifting or disappearance.

These results indicate the absence of chemical interaction between Lafutidine and formulation excipients, confirming compatibility and stability of the developed formulation.

Figure:2 IR spectrum of Lafutidine

Figure:3 IR spectrum of Lafutidine Optimised Formulation

3.4 Entrapment Efficiency

Entrapment efficiency values ranged between 89.75% and 98.47%.

The increase in polymer concentration improved entrapment efficiency due to enhanced adsorption of stabilizer molecules on nanoparticle surfaces. Formulation F12 showed maximum entrapment efficiency ($98.47 \pm 1.68\%$), indicating effective stabilization and drug incorporation.

The high entrapment efficiency may also be attributed to the presence of Pluronic F127 and SLS, which reduced drug diffusion into the external aqueous phase during nanoparticle formation.

Table:1 Entrapment efficiency of formulated Nano suspensions

Formulation code	Mean % entrapment efficiency
F1	92.47±1.24
F2	95.21±1.19
F3	94.14±1.27
F4	96.21±1.58
F5	95.61±1.67
F6	89.75±1.21
F7	96.21±1.29

3.5 Particle Size Analysis

Particle size plays a crucial role in determining dissolution rate and bioavailability. The optimized formulation F12 exhibited an average particle size of approximately 195.14 nm.

Figure:4 Particle Size Analysis

Reduction in particle size significantly increased surface area available for dissolution according to the Noyes–Whitney equation. Nanometer-sized particles also improve wettability and saturation solubility, thereby enhancing dissolution characteristics.

3.6 Zeta Potential Analysis

The optimized formulation exhibited acceptable zeta potential values indicating sufficient electrostatic stabilization of nanoparticles.

Measurement Results

Date	: Thursday, August 31, 2023 12:12 PM
Measurement Type	: Zeta Potential
Sample Name	: F12
Temperature of the Holder	: 25.0 °C
Dispersion Medium Viscosity	: 0.822 mPa·s
Conductivity	: 0.121 mS/cm
Electrode Voltage	: 2.2V

Calculation Results

Peak No.	Zeta Potential	Electrophoretic Mobility
1	-35 mV	-0.00036 cm ² /Vs
2	--- mV	--- cm ² /Vs
3	--- mV	--- cm ² /Vs

Figure:5 Zeta Potential of optimized formulation

Adequate zeta potential prevents particle aggregation and promotes long-term physical stability of the nano suspension.

3.7 Scanning Electron Microscopy

SEM images demonstrated that nanoparticles were discrete, spherical to nearly spherical in shape, and uniformly distributed without significant aggregation.

The smooth surface morphology observed confirms successful nanoparticle formation through the precipitation technique.

Figure:6 SEM image of Lafutidine Nano suspension

3.8 In Vitro Drug Release Studies

Figure:7 Dissolution parameters for the formulations F1-F12

The dissolution study demonstrated a remarkable enhancement in drug release from the optimized nano suspension compared to pure drug.

Formulation F12 released approximately 65.34% drug within the first 5 min and 98.85% within 45 min.

The rapid release can be attributed to:

- Reduced particle size
- Increased specific surface area
- Enhanced wettability by stabilizers
- Improved dispersion of drug particles

These factors collectively accelerated dissolution of Lafutidine.

3.9 Drug Release Kinetics

Drug release data were analyzed using kinetic models. The first-order model exhibited the highest correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.965$), whereas the zero-order model showed a lower correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.529$).

The findings suggest that drug release from the optimized formulation is concentration dependent and follows first-order kinetics.

4. CONCLUSION

Overall, formulation F12 containing Pluronic F127 and SLS at higher concentrations produced nanoparticles with excellent entrapment efficiency, desirable particle size, acceptable stability, and rapid dissolution performance. The study demonstrates that nano suspension technology is an effective strategy for improving dissolution behavior of poorly water-soluble Lafutidine.

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